

Chlorquinaldol and Quinoline Between MP2 and DFT Methods: Theoretical Study

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ABSTRACT

In this work, the study is focused on two important molecules in chemistry and especially in the pharmaco-medical fields. It is the chlorquinaldol and quinoline. By applying the quantum chemistry methods, the optimized geometries of the two molecules, their charge distributions, their infrared and NMR spectra in addition to their energy were obtained. The study consists in comparison of two methods: DFT and MP2. All calculations were performed with the *ab initio* method at the MP2 level of theory and DFT method.

Keywords: Ab-initio, Chlorquinaldol, DFT, MP2, NBO, Quinoline, RMN.

INTRODUCTION

Compounds containing the quinoline nucleus are also known for different therapeutic activities [1, 2] such as chloroquine (antimalarial) [3], chlorquinaldol (antibacterial and antifungal) [4] etc. (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Molecules containing a quinoline nucleue.

The chlorquinaldol [5], derived from quinoline, is an antiseptic exerting a bacteriostatic effect on many germs. It is also anti-bacterial and fungal agent in topical pharmaceutical preparations and so it was formerly used for topical treatment of skin. A monohydroxyquinoline that is quinolin-8-ol which is substituted by a methyl group at position 2 and by chlorine at positions 5 and 7 whence the name of the molecule of this aromatic compound according to IUPAC is 5, 7-dichloro-2-methyl-8-quinolinol.

The aim of this paper is to get through the theoretical methods of calculating some geometric, energy and spectroscopic properties of this base compound in pharmacotherapy. Our group, which is interested primarily in the bimolecular compounds [27], wants the results of this paper to be a platform to answer several questions such as what is the effect of the substitution of Cl atoms with Br or F atoms. What is the effect of the substitution of the OH group with NH or SH, what is its affinity to Lewis acids etc... Despite many theoretical works, no *ab-initio* studies or others of this compound have been carried out. The geometry and electronic structure of this entity have been analyzed and the comparison between the two used method calculations is examined.

COMPUTATIONAL DETAILS

The geometry optimizations have been first carried out at Hartree-Fock/6-31+G (d) level. The nature of stationary point structures

were determined by analytical frequency analysis, which also provided zero-point vibrational energies (ZPEs). ZPEs were scaled by the factor 0.9153 [6]. The harmonic vibration frequencies are also obtained at the corresponding level to characterize the stationary points as local minima or first-order saddle points. The minima structures were then re-optimized at the MP2/6-311++G (d,p) level on the one hand, and at the B3LYP/6-311++G (d,p) level on the other hand. The calculations performed by the DFT theory using the functional hybrid three parameters using Becke the functional correlation LYP (B3LYP) [7-9]. All structures reported here are minima on the potential energy surface (only positive eigenvalues of the Hessian matrix). The minimum potential energy is calculated by the Berny algorithm using redundant internal coordinates [10]. Final energies were calculated at both the B3LYP/6-311++G (d,p) + ZPEs and the MP2/6-311++G(d,p) + ZPEs levels. This last level of calculation has been recently used successfully by Gilbert on many complexes [11, 12]. The electronic structure has been done using the natural bond orbital (NBO) partitioning analysis [13, 14]. NMR properties were computed with the Gauge-Independent Atomic Orbital (GIAO). Structures used for NMR calculations should be optimized at a good level of theory. The calculations were performed using the GAUSSIAN09 suite of programs [15]. It may be mentioned that the time taken for the MP2 calculations is three times longer than the time taken for DFT calculations in this work. The production of molecules and visualization, preparation of data files for Gaussian 09 and visualization of output files, are performed using the Gauss-View 5.0 software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The optimized structures at the B3LYP/6-311++G (d,p) and MP2/6-311++G(d,p) levels for chlorquinaldol (C_1 symmetry) and quinoline (C_1 symmetry) are given in Fig. 3, Fig. 4, Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 knowing that the atoms used are designated by the Fig. 2:

Fig. 2 Atoms used in this theoretical study.

Fig. 3. Optimized geometry of chlorquinaldol (C_1 symmetry) at B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) level. Bond lengths are in \AA and bond angles in degrees.

Fig. 4. Optimized geometry of chlorquinaldol (C_1 symmetry) at MP2/6-311++G(d,p) level. Bond lengths are in \AA and bond angles in degrees.

Fig. 5. Optimized geometry of quinoline (C_1 symmetry) at B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) level. Bond lengths are in \AA .

Fig. 6. Optimized geometry of quinoline (C_1 symmetry) at MP2/6-311++G(d,p) level. Bond lengths are in \AA .

One can see from the preceding figures that all the carbon-carbon bonds within the rings have values between 1.340 \AA (experimental value of a C–C single bond [16,17]) and 1.540 \AA (experimental value of a C=C double bond [16,17]). This ensures well that the p electrons of these atoms are all delocalized. The p electron delocalization in the cycle is indeed confirmed in the case of CN bonds ($C_3 = N_{13}$ and $C_{10} = N_{13}$) where the associated lengths are between 1.279 \AA (experimental value of a C–N single bond [16,17]) and 1.465 \AA (experimental value of a C=N double bond [16,17]). All atoms participating in the cyclic skeleton are

hybridized sp^2 a result consistent with the angle values found by means of the two calculations (B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) level and MP2/6-311++G(d,p) level). It can be noticed that the examination of the C = O bond shows that part of the electron density of the O atom is involved in the conjugation within the cycle. Indeed the length of the C = O bond is between 1.220 \AA and 1.430 \AA [16, 17]. These two values correspond to the experimental lengths of a double bond CO and a simple one respectively. A comparison between the two calculation methods shows the same results at 1.5 % for bond lengths and 0.3 % for angles.

The current investigation shows that the charges are distributed differently on the two molecules (chlorquinaldol and quinoline) as it is shown in the figures 7 and 8.

Fig. 7. NBO population analysis (NBO charges) for chlorquinaldol and quinoline at B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) level.

Fig. 8. NBO population analysis (NBO charges) for chlorquinaldol and quinoline at MP2/6-311++G(d,p) level.

This is certainly due to the net difference between the two structures even if one of the other substantially drifts. In addition, passing quinoline to chlorquinaldol, a large change in the dipole moment can be noted in both direction and intensity. However, an important finding emerged from our results. It is the constancy of the following ratio:

$$\left(\frac{P_{\text{Quinoline}}}{P_{\text{Chlorquinaldol}}} \right)_{\text{DFT}} = \left(\frac{P_{\text{Quinoline}}}{P_{\text{Chlorquinaldol}}} \right)_{\text{MP2}} = 0.53$$

This ratio may optionally characterize for instance a medical or biochemical activity relative to a molecule against the other. Experimental measurements are required to prove this result. Nuclear magnetic resonance is a selective local probe can provide accurate information on close atomic environments. To conduct this study, the DFT combined with the GIAO [18-23, 26] method was used to determine the theoretical proton NMR spectrum. The comparison of the theory with experiment will allow in both to assign experimental ^1H resonances and ensure that the GIAO method reflects these chemical shifts.

The calculated and experimental data of chemical shifts are reported in Table 1, the values obtained are compared with experimental ones from the chlorquinaldol ^1H NMR spectrum (Fig. 9.) obtained in DMSO solvent.

Table 1. Chlorquinaldol : isotropic chemical shifts δ_{theo} (ppm) obtained by the method GIAO at B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) level and experimental ^1H NMR chemical shifts δ_{exp} (ppm).

Proton	H-8	H-11	H-12	H-15	H-16	H-17	H-21
Theoretical chemical shift δ_{theo} (ppm)	7.575	8.349	7.437	2.798	3.048	2.529	8.360
Experimental chemical shift δ_{exp} (ppm)	7.728	8.365	7.628	2.758	3.050	2.509	8.387

Fig. 9. Chlorquinaldol experimental ^1H NMR spectrum performed in DMSO solvent [24].

Fig. 10. Chlorquinaldol theoretical ^1H NMR spectrum computed with GIAO method at B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) level.

The data in Table 1 can be drawn a curve of experimental chemical shifts based on theoretical chemical shifts, we got a right to the following equation

Fig. 11. Graphical correlation between the chemical shift values calculated by the GIAO at B3LYP/6-311++G (d,p) level and experimental ones for chlorquinaldol.

The analysis of the linear regression provides a slope of 1.019. This shows the linearity between the theoretical and experimental data. The regression coefficient is $R^2 = 0.999$. This indicates a good match between theory and experimental measurement.

399.65 MHz
21.1 mg : 0.5 ml CDCl_3

Fig. 12. Quinoline experimental ^1H NMR spectrum performed in CDCl_3 solvent [25].

Fig. 13. Quinoline theoretical ^1H NMR spectrum computed with GIAO method at B3LYP/6-311++G (d,p) level.

Fig. 14. Graphical correlation between the chemical shift values calculated by the GIAO at B3LYP/6-311++G (d,p) level and experimental ones for quinoline.

Table 2. Quinoline : isotropic chemical shifts δ_{theo} (ppm) obtained by the method GIAO at B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) level and experimental ^1H NMR chemical shifts δ_{exp} (ppm).

Proton	H-8/F	H-11/C	H-12/G	H-14/B	H-15/E	H-16/D	H-17/A
Theoretical chemical shift δ_{theo} (ppm)	7.672	8.133	7.366	8.447	7.906	7.901	9.123
Experimental chemical shift δ_{exp} (ppm)	7.548	8.123	7.394	8.153	7.721	7.816	8.923

Table 3. Chlorquinaldol : frequencies and intensities of the absorption bands associated with active vibration modes in infrared

Band	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Frequency (cm^{-1})	587	1050	1373	1479	1622	1833	4013
Intensity	352	257	350	525	700	375	475

Table 4. Quinoline: frequencies and intensities of the absorption bands associated with active vibration modes in infrared.

Band	1	2	3	4
Frequency (cm^{-1})	906	1073	1802	3382
intensity	520	155	160	355

The same study applied to the quinoline led to the same result: good linearity and correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.997$) between theoretical and experimental values as is shown by Table 2 and Figures 12, 13 and 14.

On the other hand, one can extract important information about the infrared activity of both molecules studied. Indeed, the theoretical spectra of the vibrations of the two entities studied are shown below in Figures 15 and 16

Fig. 15. Theoretical infrared spectrum of chlorquinaldol computed at B3LYP/6-311++G (d,p) level.

Fig. 16. Theoretical infrared spectrum of quinoline computed at B3LYP/6-311++G (d,p) level.

Fig. 17. Vibration modes corresponding to the bands 1 to 7 (identified in Table 3) for chlorquinaldol

In examining the theoretical infrared spectra of the two molecules, it can be noticed that existence of several absorption bands with the most intense are those reported in tables 3 and 4. Each absorption band is associated with a mode of vibration as it is shown in Figures 17 and 18. The appearance of these bands in the infrared spectra inform us that all recently cited vibration modes are active in infrared spectroscopy because they induce a change in the electrical dipole moment of the molecules studied. As perspective, it can be said that these vibration modes can also be active in Raman spectroscopy provided they lead to a change in the polarizability of the molecules subjects in this study.

Table 5. Quinoline: frequencies and intensities of the absorption bands associated with active vibration modes in infrared.

	Chlorquinaldol		Quinoline	
	DFT	MP2	DFT	MP2
E_0 (kcal/mol)	-901.0297 $\times 10^3$	-901.0230 $\times 10^3$	-252.2826 $\times 10^3$	-250.6518 $\times 10^3$
E_{ZPE} (kcal/mol)	100,3172	100,3172	91,3311	91,32801
E_{ZPE} (scaled) (kcal/mol)	91,8204	91,8204	83,5954	83,5925
E_{tot} (kcal/mol)	-900.9379 $\times 10^3$	-900.9312 $\times 10^3$	-252.1990 $\times 10^3$	-250.5682 $\times 10^3$

E_0	electronic energy without counting the zero-point energy
E_{ZPE}	zero-point energy
E_{ZPE} (scaled)	zero-point energy scaled by the factor 0.9153 [16]
E_{tot}	total electronic energy taking into account the scaled zero-point energy

Table 5 presents the computed energies for the two molecules studied. It is evident that the chlorquinaldol is more stable energetically than quinoline one, this is due to impact of the donor atoms of chlorine and oxygen atom on the hydroxy group. Indeed, in the chlorquinaldol these donor atoms by mesomeric effect involved largely to stabilize the molecule cycles. The same table shows that the values of the total energy of each of the two molecules are very similar although the methods of calculation used are different. In quantitative terms, the relative error is 0.6 % for the quinoline whereas it is only 8.0×10^{-4} % in the case of chlorquinaldol.

CONCLUSIONS

In summary, the study has provided a theoretical investigation on chlorquinaldol and quinoline which are two molecules in chemical and medicated use. Theoretically it has been shown that both molecules have a real existence since the harmonic vibration frequencies calculation provides no negative frequency. It was found that the Cl atoms and the OH group in the chlorquinaldol provide increased stability relative to the latter quinoline which is reflected by the net difference between their energies. These energies, as well as the geometric parameters, imply that the DFT method produces results as good as formidable perturbation method MP2. In examining the proton NMR, theoretical chemical shifts obtained at calculation used, are similar to 100% with experimental ones, which is another victory of the DFT method in quantum chemistry.

REFERENCES

1. P. R. Graves, J. J. Kwiek, P. Fadden, R. Ray, K. Hardeman, A. M. Coley, M. Foley, T. A. J. Haystead, Discovery of novel targets of quinoline drugs in the human purine binding proteome, *Mol. Pharmacol.* 62 (2002) 1364-1372
2. L. W. Scheibel, A. Adler, Antimalarial activity of selected aromatic chelators. II. Substituted quinolines and quinoline-N-oxides, *Mol. Pharmacol.* 20 (1981) 218-223
3. J. M. Gostner, S. Schröcksnadel, K. Becker, M. Jenny, H. Schennach, F. Überall, D. Fuchs, Antimalarial drug chloroquine counteracts activation of indoleamine (2,3)-dioxygenase activity in human PBMC, *J Allergy Clin Immunol.* 2 (2012) 241-245.
4. H.L. Kolmer, E.A. Taketomi, K.C. Hazen, E. Hughs, B.B. Wilson, T.A. Platts-Mills, Effect of combined antibacterial and antifungal treatment in severe atopic dermatitis, *J Allergy Clin Immunol.* 98 (1996) 702-707.
5. R.B. Chaudhari, S.S. Rindhe, Synthesis and antimicrobial activities of novel 8-(1-alkyl/alkylsulphonyl/alkoxycarbonyl-benzimidazol-2-ylmethoxy)-5-hloroquinolines, *J. Serb. Chem. Soc.* 76 (2011) 1199-1206
6. J.A. Pople, H.B. Schlegel, J.S. Binkly, M.J. Frisch, R.A. Whiteside, R.F. Hout, W.J. Hehre, Molecular orbital studies of vibrational frequencies, *Int. J. Quantum Chem. Symp.* 15 (1981) 269-278.
7. A.D. Becke, Density-functional exchange-energy approximation with correct asymptotic behavior, *Phys. Rev. A*, 38 (1988) 3098-3100.

8. A.D. Becke, A new mixing of Hartree-Fock and local density-functional theories, *Journal of Chemical Physics.* 98 (1993) 1372-1377.
9. C. Lee, W. Yang, R.G. Parr, Development of the Colle-Salvetti Correlation-Energy Formula into a Functional of the Electron Density, *Phys. Rev. B*, 37 (1988) 785-789.
10. C. Peng, P.Y. Ayala, H.B. Schlegel, M.J. Frisch, Using redundant internal coordinates to optimize equilibrium geometries and transition states, *Journal of Computational Chemistry*, 17 (1996) 49-56.
11. T.M. Gilbert, Tests of the MP2 Model and Various DFT Models in Predicting the Structures and B-N Bond Dissociation Energies of Amine-Boranes (X3C)mH3-mB-N(CH3)nH3-n (X = H, F; m = 0-3; n = 0-3): Poor Performance of the B3LYP Approach for Dative B-N Bonds, *J. Phys. Chem. A.* 108 (2004) 2550-2554
12. M. Cherkaoui, A. Boutalib, Ab initio Investigation of the Substituent Effect of the Alane Complexes, *Internet Electronic Journal of Molecular Design*, 5 (2006) 1-9.
13. F. Weinhold, C.R. Landis, Introduction to Natural Bond Orbitals, NBO 5.0 Program, and Recent Extensions of Localized Bonding Concepts, *Chem. Ed.: Res. & Pract.* 2 (2001) 91-104.
14. A. E. Reed, L. A. Curtiss, F. Weinhold, Intermolecular interactions from a natural bond orbital, donor-acceptor viewpoint, *Chem. Rev.* 88 (1988) 899-926.
15. M.J.Frisch et al Gaussian 09, Revision A.02. Gaussian Inc., Wallingford CT, 2009.
16. D.R. Lide, CRC Handbook of Chemistry and Physics, ed. CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL, (2005).
17. F.H. Allen, O. Kennard, D.G. Watson, L. Brammer, A.G. Orpen, Tables of bond Lengths determined by X-Ray and Neutron Diffraction. Part 1. Bond Lengths in Organic Compounds, *J. Chem. Soc. Perkin Trans. II* (1987) S1-S19.
18. F. London, The quantic theory of inter-atomic currents in aromatic combinations, *J. Phys. Radium.* 8 (1937) 397-409.
19. R. Mc Weeny, Perturbation Theory for Fock-Dirac Density Matrix, *Phys. Rev.* 126 (1962) 1028-1034.
20. R. Ditchfield, Self-consistent perturbation theory of diamagnetism. 1. Gauge-invariant LCAO method for N.M.R. chemical shifts, *Mol. Phys.* 27 (1974) 789-807.
21. K. Wolinski, J. F. Hilton, and P. Pulay, Efficient Implementation of the Gauge-Independent Atomic Orbital Method for NMR Chemical Shift Calculations, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 112 (1990) 8251-8260.
22. J. R. Cheeseman, G.W. Trucks, T.A. Keith, M.J. Frisch, A Comparison of Models for Calculating Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Shielding Tensors, *J. Chem. Phys.* 104 (1996) 5497-5509.
23. M. Şenyel, Ö. Alver, C. Parlak, ¹H, ¹³C, ¹⁵N NMR and nJ(C, H) coupling constants investigation of 3-Piperidino-propylamine: A combined experimental and

- theoretical study, *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 71 (2008) 830-834
24. S419201-Chlorquinaldol-HNMR-Selleckchem PO Box 300287, Houston TX 77230 USA.
25. Quinoline (CAS 91-22-5) ¹H NMR, chemicalbook.
26. A. Zeroual, A. Benharref, A. El Hajbi, Experimental and theoretical study of the chemical shifts (¹³C NMR) of some cyclic products by the method DFT, *International Journal of Innovation and Applied Studies*, 7 (2014) 795-801.
27. M. Cherkaoui, A. Boutalib, A Theoretical investigation of furan-AIX3, pyrrole-AIX3 and thiophene-AIX3 (X = H, F, Cl, Br) interactions, *Electronic Journal of Chemistry: Orbital*, 4 (2012) 235-244.

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